

MAST: Phylogenetic Inference with Mixtures Across Sites and Trees

Details of how the parameters were simulated in all the simulation experiments

All trees were simulated by IQ-TREE version 2 (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) with the option '-r'. This simulates a random Yule tree with branch lengths drawn from an exponential distribution with a mean of 0.1, a minimum of 0.001, and a maximum of 0.999. The parameters of the GTR model R were the values of six random integers uniformly drawn between 5 and 50 and normalized according to the value of $G \leftrightarrow T$ such that the $G \leftrightarrow T$ rate was always equal to 1.0. The gamma rate H was drawn randomly from an exponential distribution with a mean of 1.0. The set of nucleotide frequencies F was the proportions between four integers uniformly drawn between 1 and 10.

When a dataset was simulated under m trees, the dataset contained different proportions of the lengths of each of the m alignments. The proportions of the lengths of each of the m alignments simulated from each of the m trees were the ratios of m random integers drawn from a uniform distribution between 1 and 10.

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: This figure presents the performance of the MAST model with unlinked parameters across all trees, specifically, MAST submodel 1, using the true topologies on 100K-length data sets simulated under the MAST model with unlinked parameters. Each tree has its own set of branch lengths, substitution matrix, nucleotide frequencies, and gamma parameters. The data sets were simulated with varying numbers of topologies (2, 3, 5, and 10) and numbers of sequences (6, 7, 10, and 20) in the alignments. (A) the root-mean-squared error distribution for tree weights, (B) branch lengths, (C) GTR parameters, (D) nucleotide frequencies, (E) the absolute error distribution for the shape parameter α in the Gamma distribution, and (F) the distribution of the difference in BIC values, represented as BIC - BICO, between the MAST model (BIC) and a standard single-tree model (BICO), are shown. The pattern suggests that larger tree sizes and fewer input trees contribute to enhanced estimation accuracy. It also highlights that larger tree sizes tend to have a larger negative difference between the BIC values of the MAST and single-tree models. This suggests that the MAST model exhibits a stronger preference over the standard single-tree model. Note that the substantial error for parameter alpha (α) in the data sets with smaller trees and numerous input trees suggests minimal heterogeneity across the sites.

Simulation 1 results: Performance of MAST Model with unlinked Parameters on 5K, 10K, and 50K-length data sets

Supplementary Figure 2: This figure presents the performance of the MAST model with unlinked parameters across all trees, specifically, MAST submodel 1, using the true topologies on 5K, 10K, and 50K-length data sets simulated under the MAST model with unlinked parameters. Each tree has its own set of branch lengths, substitution matrix, nucleotide frequencies, and gamma parameters. The data sets were simulated with varying numbers of topologies (2, 3, 5, and 10) and numbers of sequences (6, 7, 10, and 20) in the alignments. Among the input trees, the first tree differed from the other trees by 1, 2, or 3 SPR moves. The root-mean-squared error distribution for tree weights for (A) 5K-length data sets, (B) 10K-length data sets, (C) 50K-length data sets, and the distribution of the difference in BIC values, represented as BIC - BIC0, between the MAST model (BIC) and a standard single-tree model (BIC0) for (D) 5K-length data sets, (E) 10K-length data sets, and (F) 50K-length data sets, are shown. The pattern suggests that larger tree sizes, longer sequences, fewer input trees, and more SPR-move differences from the first tree lead to better estimation accuracy. It also highlights that larger tree sizes and longer sequences tend to have a larger negative difference between the BIC values of the MAST and single-tree models. This suggests that the MAST model exhibits a stronger preference over the standard single-tree model for all 5K, 10K, and 50K-length data sets.

Simulation 2 results: Performance of MAST Model with linked Parameters on 100K-length data sets

Supplementary Figure 3: This figure presents the performance of the MAST model with linked parameters across all trees, specifically, MAST submodel 6, using the true topologies on 100K-length data sets simulated under the MAST model with linked parameters. Each tree has its own set of branch lengths, while all share the same substitution matrix, nucleotide frequencies, and gamma parameters. The data sets were simulated with varying numbers of topologies (2, 3, 5, and 10) and numbers of sequences (6, 7, 10, and 20) in the alignments. (A) the root-mean-squared error distribution for tree weights, (B) branch lengths, (C) GTR parameters, (D) nucleotide frequencies, (E) the absolute error distribution for the shape parameter α in the Gamma distribution, and (F) the distribution of the difference in BIC values, represented as $BIC - BIC_0$, between the MAST model (BIC) and a standard single-tree model (BIC_0), are shown. The pattern suggests that larger tree sizes and fewer input trees contribute to enhanced estimation accuracy. It also highlights that larger tree sizes tend to have a larger negative difference between the BIC values of the MAST and single-tree models. This suggests that the MAST model exhibits a stronger preference over the standard single-tree model.

Simulation 4 results: Performance of MAST model with unlinked parameters on the various-length data sets simulated under a single tree

Supplementary Figure 4: This figure illustrates the performance of the MAST model with unlinked parameters on data sets simulated under a single tree. We used an unconstrained MAST model in which each class has its own substitution matrices, base frequencies, and rate heterogeneity model. The data sets were simulated with varying numbers of topologies (2, 3, 5, and 10) and numbers of sequences (6, 7, 10, and 20) in the alignments. Among the input trees, the first tree differed from the other trees by 1, 2, or 3 SPR moves. The percentage of times the true trees with the highest weights for (A) 5K-length data sets, (B) 10K-length data sets, (C) 50K-length data sets; and the distribution of the difference in BIC values, represented as BIC - BICO, between the MAST model (BIC) and a standard single-tree model (BICO) for (D) 5K-length data sets, (E) 10K-length data sets, (F) 50K-length data sets, are shown. Overall, the observed trend highlights that fewer trees, larger tree sizes and longer lengths tend to have a higher chance that the true trees have the highest weights and a larger positive difference between the BIC values of the MAST and single-tree models. This suggests that the standard single-tree model exhibits a stronger preference over the MAST model. This sounds and is sensible because the data set was simulated under a single tree.

Simulation 5 results: Performance of MAST model with linked parameters on the 100K-length data sets simulated under a single tree

Supplementary Figure 5: This figure illustrates the performance of the MAST model with linked parameters on data sets simulated under a single tree. We used a constrained MAST model in which all classes share the same substitution matrices, base frequencies, and rate heterogeneity model. The data sets were simulated with varying numbers of topologies (2, 3, 5, and 10) and numbers of sequences (6, 7, 10, and 20) in the alignments. Among the input trees, the first tree differed from the other trees by 1, 2, or 3 SPR moves. (A) The percentage of times the true trees with the highest weights, and (B) the distribution of the difference in BIC values, represented as BIC - BIC0, between the MAST model (BIC) and a standard single-tree model (BIC0) are shown. Overall, the observed trend highlights that fewer trees and larger tree sizes tend to have a higher chance that the true trees have the highest weights and a larger positive difference between the BIC values of the MAST and single-tree models. This suggests that the standard single-tree model exhibits a stronger preference over the MAST model. This sounds and is sensible because the data set was simulated under a single tree.

Simulation 6 results: Performance of the linked MAST model with all possible 5-tip trees on the data sets simulated under two equally-weighted 5-tip trees

Supplementary Figure 6: This figure shows the tree weight distribution for each tree reported from the linked MAST model when applied to a 100K-long 5-taxon data set with all 15 potential topologies. The data set was simulated using two equally weighted 5-tip trees, T1 and T2. Here, T1 and T2 represent the actual trees used for simulation, whereas F1 to F13 denote the remaining 13 trees not used in the simulation. The results highlight that the MAST model assigns the highest weights to the two true trees.

Simulation 6 results: The changes in BIC values when trees are sequentially added to the MAST model on the data sets simulated under two equally-weighted 5-tip trees

Supplementary Figure 7: This figure shows the changes in the BIC values when trees are sequentially added to the MAST model when applied to the 100K-long data simulated under two evenly weighted 5-tip trees. The figure shows (A) the resulting BIC values from the MAST model for a single data set and (B) the distribution of the changes in the BIC values across 100 data sets, after adding each tree sequentially when applying the MAST model to the data sets. Initially, the two true trees are used with the MAST model. Then, other trees are added based on the descending order of tree weights from an analysis involving all 15 potential trees. The figure shows that the BIC values from the MAST model using the two real trees are considerably lower than that of the standard one-tree model, and the BIC values increase gradually when more non-real trees are considered. For these data sets, in 98% of the cases, the MAST model with two real trees was the optimal model according to the BIC value.

Supplementary Figure 8: (A) Gene trees with introgression rate $r \in \{0.0, 0.1, \dots, 1.0\}$ were simulated in the direction from lineages 2 to 4 by ms under the coalescent model. The edge lengths are in coalescent time; (B) Three possible topologies for the simulated introgression dataset. T_{E1} is the species tree while some sites may evolve under the topologies T_{E2} and T_{E3} due to the introgression and incomplete lineage sorting.

Supplementary Figure 9: Nine topologies for empirical dataset C. T_{C9} is the commonly accepted species tree.

Supplementary Figure 10: Three topologies for empirical dataset D. T_{D1} is the commonly accepted species tree.

Supplementary Tables

Topology	Number of genes (Gene tree %)		Sum of gene lengths		Total number of variable sites		Total number of parsimony informative sites	
T_{A1}	316	19.8%	302,416	18.7%	7,557	19.9%	430	17.7%
T_{A2}	320	20.1%	278,066	17.2%	6,259	16.5%	339	13.9%
T_{A3}	959	60.1%	1,038,024	64.1%	24,136	63.6%	1,662	68.4%
Total	1,595		1,618,506		37,952		2,431	

Supplementary Table 1: Detailed information of the genes in empirical dataset A. T_{A3} is the commonly accepted species tree.

Topology	Number of genes (Gene tree %)		Sum of gene lengths		Total number of variable sites		Total number of parsimony informative sites	
T_{B1}	499	31.2%	438,469	26.9%	8,218	26.6%	214	17.6%
T_{B2}	298	18.6%	298,016	18.3%	5,817	18.8%	176	14.5%
T_{B3}	802	50.2%	892,678	54.8%	16,857	54.6%	824	67.9%
Total	1,599		1,629,163		30,892		1,214	

Supplementary Table 2: Detailed information of the genes in empirical dataset B. T_{B3} is the commonly accepted species tree.

Topology	Number of genes (Gene tree %)		Sum of gene lengths		Total number of variable sites		Total number of parsimony informative sites	
T_{C1}	53	3.4%	45,687	2.9%	2,014	3.2%	1,216	3.0%
T_{C2}	102	6.6%	88,269	5.6%	3,398	5.4%	2,087	5.2%
T_{C3}	154	10.0%	154,860	9.9%	5,883	9.4%	3,701	9.2%
T_{C4}	67	4.4%	59,598	3.8%	2,434	3.9%	1,525	3.8%
T_{C5}	118	7.7%	93,530	6.0%	3,664	5.9%	2,371	5.9%
T_{C6}	132	8.6%	127,011	8.1%	4,758	7.6%	2,960	7.4%
T_{C7}	176	11.4%	196,128	12.5%	7,943	12.7%	5,055	12.6%
T_{C8}	258	16.8%	252,405	16.1%	9,489	15.2%	6,140	15.3%
T_{C9}	479	31.1%	546,967	35.0%	22,866	36.6%	15,147	37.7%
Total	1,539		1,564,455		62,449		40,202	

Supplementary Table 3: Detailed information of the genes in empirical dataset C. T_{C9} is the commonly accepted species tree.

	((MF,MN),MM)	((MM,MN),MF)	((MF,MM),MN)	Sum
((G,C),H)	T_{C1} 0.4%	T_{C2} 7.0%	T_{C3} 8.4%	15.8%
((H,G),C)	T_{C4} 7.7%	T_{C5} 2.9%	T_{C6} 18.3%	28.9%
((H,C),G)	T_{C7} 13.0%	T_{C8} 8.7%	T_{C9} 33.6%	55.3%
Sum	21.1%	18.6%	60.3%	

Supplementary Table 4: The sum of the proportions for different groups of topologies according to the results of submodel 1 on empirical data C. H - Human; C - Chimpanzee; G - Gorilla; MM - *Macaca mulatta*; MF - *Macaca fascicularis*; MN - *Macaca nemestrina*. Note that the last decimal place of the sums may not match due to the round-up effect.

	((MF,MN),MM)	((MM,MN),MF)	((MF,MM),MN)	Sum
((G,C),H)	T _{C1} 0.4%	T _{C2} 10.4%	T _{C3} 8.2%	19.0%
((H,G),C)	T _{C4} 2.1%	T _{C5} 2.5%	T _{C6} 14.0%	18.5%
((H,C),G)	T _{C7} 13.1%	T _{C8} 8.4%	T _{C9} 41.1%	62.6%
Sum	15.5%	21.2%	63.3%	

Supplementary Table 5: The sum of the proportions for different groups of topologies according to the results of submodel 2 on empirical data C. H - Human; C - Chimpanzee; G - Gorilla; MM - *Macaca mulatta*; MF - *Macaca fascicularis*; MN - *Macaca nemestrina*. Note that the last decimal place of the sums may not match due to the round-up effect.

Topology	Number of genes (Gene tree %)		Sum of gene lengths		Total number of variable sites		Total number of parsimony informative sites	
T_{D1}	295	37.06%	329,864	36.06%	30,823	36.72%	3,064	36.69%
T_{D2}	258	32.41%	302,224	33.04%	27,225	32.43%	2,692	32.24%
T_{D3}	243	30.53%	282,703	30.90%	25,903	30.85%	2,594	31.07%
Other	761	---	695,964	---	56,689	---	5,426	---
$T_{D1}+T_{D2}+T_{D3}$	796		914,791		83,951		8,350	

Supplementary Table 6: Detailed information of the genes in empirical dataset D. T_{D1} is the commonly accepted species tree.